

Leaving no one behind!? Exploring how developers currently engage communities in onshore wind energy deployments

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Abstract

Community and stakeholder engagement was widely discussed at the WindEurope Annual Event 2023 – an important convention for the European wind energy industry and policymakers. Interviews with four European wind energy developers and a social scientist at the convention reveal that developers' community engagement practices vary in their extent and purpose. In line with the literature, three approaches could be distinguished across developers. The first approach, instrumental engagement, focuses on overcoming public opposition through information provision and dialogue without actively involving residents in project planning. The second approach, normative engagement, recognizes the value of transparent and fair engagement, considering residents' concerns and feedback but with limitations on their influence over project decisions. The third approach, substantive engagement, seeks to empower communities and give them ownership over projects, aiming to improve social outcomes and make them part of the energy transition. While community engagement practices have improved, challenges remain, and a cultural change in the wind energy sector towards viewing communities as collaborators rather than opponents is needed. Educating engineers on the social impacts of wind energy and fostering interdisciplinary collaborations can contribute to more meaningful and successful community engagement in wind energy projects.

Keywords: community engagement, wind energy, developer, onshore

1. Introduction

The WindEurope Annual Event is the largest and most important convention for the European wind energy industry and policymakers. As such, it primarily focuses on technological and regulatory aspects of wind energy development. However, during the 2023 edition, at least one panel discussion was dedicated to community and stakeholder engagement. The topic also kept creeping up in other sessions, such as permitting and auctioning design. Does it suggest that after years of urging from researchers, citizens, and civil society organizations, the wind energy

sector finally recognizes the importance of involving communities and other societal stakeholders better in wind energy projects? Four European wind energy developers and a social scientist from the Technical University of Denmark (DTU) were interviewed during the WindEurope Annual Event 2023 to better understand developers' current community engagement practices. While all developers assured that they pursued a comprehensive community engagement approach, they differed in how they viewed the purpose of community engagement and the role of citizens and developers. This has implications for how they engage with communities. Three approaches could be distinguished

that align with existing research: 1) instrumental engagement, 2) normative engagement, and 3) substantive engagement (Aitken et al., 2014). Instrumental engagement aims at avoiding, reducing, or overcoming public opposition. Normative engagement is based on the premise that involving residents is the 'right thing to do' and that residents' knowledge can help improve a project. In substantive engagement, residents are seen as agents of the process, and the ultimate goal is to improve social outcomes more widely. The following will illustrate the three approaches based on the interview findings.

2. Engagement practices

2.1 Instrumental engagement: "It's not a joint process."

The first developer, subscribing to an instrumental approach, sees engagement as a way to overcome resistance. Residents are informed about the proposed development, and their questions and queries are answered, but their feedback is not considered in the plans, and they cannot actively shape the project. According to the developer, "It is not a joint process, but we plan and inform, and then we enter into a dialogue" (Developer 1). In the eyes of the developer, the deployment of onshore wind energy has to be discussed very intensely with the local public: "With the exception of offshore, renewable energies are called decentralized energies. That means they are close to people and are visible. If something is big and visible, it will be discussed" (Developer 1). The developer views conflict and local resistance as something unavoidable that has to be dealt with, although they recognize that it mainly comes from a loud minority: "Very often you have a situation where a loud minority tries to be heard, and the silent majority is not interested in being heard. And that creates the impression that the majority is against it, which is not the case" (Developer 1). The developer's experience aligns with research findings showing that opponents of a wind energy project are more likely to become active than residents who tolerate or support it (Hübner et al., 2020). However, rather than proactively asking residents about their concerns, the developer mainly reverts to information provision. Usually, for each project, they set up a website that details the plans and allows residents to submit questions; they invite residents living within a given radius around the proposed wind park to a public event with information booths – what they call marketplace-; and they show augmented reality visualizations of the wind park. Julia Kirch Kirkegaard, the DTU researcher, criticizes the information deficit perspective of the developer as too limited and insufficient:

"There is really this clash somehow between facts and feeling – developers often from technical

sciences believe in the numbers and the simulations. So if [residents] talk about feelings, the [developers] would provide the proper numbers and graphs to convince them that they should not be worried. And local communities might not be bothered about the numbers. They don't trust them necessarily. We need to move beyond that deficit model and figure out how we can discuss these things and make space for feelings. We need to understand that people's concerns are real because they are." – Julia Kirch Kirkegaard, Social Scientist

2.2 Normative engagement: "We are not trying to force our will on them."

The second developer, whose engagement approach can be classified as normative, recognizes the important role of feelings when it comes to wind deployment. The developer acknowledges that not knowing what is going to happen can give rise to fears, and communities might be worried that the project developer will not be looking after their interests. The developer attempts to address those fears: "So we will try and work with them to understand what their concerns are and factor that into the plans for what we are doing moving forward" (Developer 2). Consistent with research showing the relevance of a transparent and fair planning process (e.g., Firestone et al., 2018; Hübner et al., 2023; Walker & Baxter, 2017), the developer understands that good community engagement is crucial to successful projects: "Well, if you're not listening to your stakeholders, then you're a fool. Because ultimately, if anti-sponsors crystallize around a project, it can delay the project massively. It can mean the project is unsuccessful. So, you know, sometimes if you ignore people like that, you cut off your nose to spite your face" (Developer 2). The developer, therefore, tries to listen to residents' concerns and considers their feedback: "We like to think of ourselves as a company who looks to engage the local community because we are not trying to force our will on them. We want to do good by the planet, but we also want to do good by the communities as well" (Developer 2).

Some ways in which the developer benefits locals is through discounted local electricity prices, by helping the community with small investments (e.g., repairing the roof of the youth center, providing a minibus), or by hiring local contractors or businesses during the wind park construction. In some cases, the design of wind projects was even changed following consultation with locals: "If The Rambler [a UK hiking association] need to preserve a line of sight, very often with turbines, you can move them around to a certain extent. There are optimum positions because the land shapes the wind. But at the same time, you have to give and take" (Developer 2). Nevertheless, there are limits to how much the developer lets stakeholders shape the project: "We don't

go there saying, 'we're going to build a wind farm,' and we walk away building a solar farm because they didn't like wind. You know, that's not really what you're trying to do" (Developer 2). The developer also recognizes that the effectiveness of community engagement is limited and that acceptance might dwindle with an increase in turbine density:

"It may be socially acceptable to have a wind farm A and maybe later wind farm B, but where the issues often lie and where the community really sort of catalyzes itself in a negative way is around wind farms A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H, I. And you can go to some places, and the wind farms are so close to each other that they actually merge. So it becomes a mass of turbines. Now we need that [for climate mitigation], but at the same time, I can empathize with the local people who would be objecting." – Developer 2

2.3 Substantive engagement: "We have a responsibility to make them a part of the project."

Acknowledging that it is difficult to sustain public support for the required large-scale wind developments, the third and fourth developers are convinced that the energy transition can only be successful if they involve citizens and give them some ownership over the projects. They are intrinsically motivated to engage communities meaningfully and empower them: "The wind energy sector is coming to an understanding that we, of course, need to involve citizens. And I think that if we are not doing that and if we're not struggling to go the extra mile, then we get some kind of opposition to the green transition in general" (Developer 3). The third developer believes that it will be easier for people to support the energy transition if they "see that they can be a part of it and not something that they are forced into." Social scientist Julia Kirch Kirkegaard agrees with this notion:

"So it has really become this big business and a matter of earning a lot of profits, but there's very little space for local communities, and I believe that can actually also cause concerns about the visual impact and the noise and so on because people don't think they are part of it so much any longer. So it's more like these foreign companies coming and taking their energy resource from them and taking all the benefits." – Julia Kirch Kirkegaard, Social Scientist

The third developer is well aware that they are intruding into residents' living spaces and, therefore, feels responsible for involving communities:

"We are coming as a huge company with a huge technological site in an area where people have lived for a long time and maybe even moved there because they liked it as it is, and we interfere with their community. And of course, we have a responsibility to make them a part of the project, and hopefully they can get some kind of ownership in the project." – Developer 3

The developer and the local community explore together the local needs and how they can be met. Sometimes, they build infrastructure inside the wind park, such as mountain bike lanes or shelters for hikers, or they set up a benefit fund for the local community, which then gets to decide how to spend the money so that it benefits the community as a whole. Municipalities have also been given financial shares in wind parks before. Finally, the third developer has even offered a local municipality to veto a project, which the municipality did not do. This relates to the notion of legal vs. ethical acceptability raised by the fourth developer, who believes that one should not realize a project if it is unethical, even when one has the permits and legal rights to do so: "A responsible company should not do something because it is legal, it should do something when it is ethical" (Developer 4). Despite the developer's strong efforts to 'do the right thing,' they realize that they engage in trade-offs:

"What is more relevant: the opinion of three families or climate protection for the whole planet? Who draws the line? We follow the mitigation hierarchy: avoid, mitigate, compensate. If we think at the end of the day, you can bear the risk, we go ahead. It happens that we build projects with some level of opposition. We don't get a 100%. That is the reality" – Developer 4

However, in general, the third and fourth developers have experienced that an early, transparent, and genuine engagement works better for the community and themselves:

"We see a more positive reaction towards our projects when we come there, involve them, say that we're interested in them being a part of the project. When they can see that they get some benefit out of the project as well, and it's not just us coming there doing a project. Then the project also goes through more easily, and we don't have that much of an opposition against our projects." – Developer 3

2.4 Current practices summarized: More community engagement but not always meaningful

The scoping interviews with three major and one smaller European wind energy developer show that community

engagement is a hot topic. While the developers engage communities earlier (usually before applying for a permit) and more than used to be the case, their approaches differ widely. Some are intrinsically motivated because they believe that communities should become a part of projects and the energy transition more widely, giving them a chance to develop some felt ownership for the project (i.e., substantive engagement). In contrast, other developers engage communities because it is expected of them and increases the chance of project success (i.e., instrumental engagement). Even others' approach falls somewhere in the middle, taking residents' feedback into account without giving them ownership over the process (i.e., normative engagement). Developers' approaches also differed in whether they only engage with residents living in a certain radius or with everyone whose interests are affected by the proposed project, which the literature refers to as 'community-of-place' vs. 'community-of-interest' (Baxter et al., 2020). For the latter, stakeholder mapping is used to identify affected stakeholders, including residents, local organizations, NGOs, local businesses, and associations (e.g., hikers and birdwatchers). The aim is to make the engagement process more inclusive and meaningful.

Something that all interviewed developers agreed on is that community engagement has to be tailored to the local community. The chosen approach, timeline, and which stakeholders are involved depends on the situational context, such as whether already other wind farms exist in the area, how active the local community and municipality are in supporting or opposing wind projects, and whether they even want to be engaged in the project. The second developer said: "You can't take a brushstroke approach to development and community engagement; it just doesn't work because it's about relationships, and you only get good relationships by investing time in them." The third developer pointed out that this bears challenges because one cannot develop a template for all community engagement processes. Nonetheless, some universal principles, as outlined here, can make community engagement more meaningful and successful.

3. Moving forward: The wind energy sector needs a cultural (and regulatory?) change

While the wind energy sector started to acknowledge the importance of community engagement, a cultural change¹ is still needed to allow developers to see communities as collaborators and not opponents. The third developer emphasizes how important this mindset change is for a

sustainable transition: "We need to see [communities] as very important stakeholders to us. The wind industry needs to realize that we get better, more sustainable solutions if we involve the communities. So in the long run, if we want to have support for the green transition, we, of course, need the people" (Developer 3). Julia Kirch Kirkegaard from DTU agrees with this notion and adds that educating engineers – as early as in university – about the social impacts of wind energy is important for enabling such change. More interdisciplinary research and collaborations between industry and academia on this topic are also crucial, for example, by inviting more researchers to the WindEurope Annual Events. In Kirch Kirkegaard's experience, developers' rather technical mindset and approach can be a bottleneck because they try to fix an inherently psychological or social problem with a technical solution. For example, concerns about noise impacts are often entangled with perceiving the planning process as unfair (Hübner et al., 2019; Pohl et al., 2018). Kirch Kirkegaard also cautions that the economic interests of developers might make it hard for residents to trust their intentions. Trust in responsible actors is strongly related to project acceptance (Hübner et al., 2023): "It's a delicate balancing act, [developers] should be aware of their own role and understand that people might have pre-conceptions of their agenda. It would be important [for developers] to argue how they try to reduce this bias" (Julia Kirch Kirkegaard, Social Scientist).

The DTU researcher further criticizes that regulations are limited to technical standards, such as thresholds for loudness, and do not account for residents' lived experiences, which are usually more predictive of project acceptance. At the WindEurope Annual Event 2023, it was debated whether regulations could improve community engagement. The consensus across the panels appeared that community engagement should not be forced through legislation because it will make it difficult to tailor the engagement process to the context. Instead, it was argued that regulations should focus on avoiding harm (e.g., ecologically), and developers should outperform each other with creative solutions for community engagement during renewable energy auctions. However, practical examples show that legislation can still provide a fruitful framework for meaningful community engagement, for instance, by setting requirements regarding community benefits. This has been achieved in Ireland with the mandatory Community Benefit Fund for all renewable energy projects and in the East-German state Brandenburg with a law from 2019 requiring developers to pay 10,000 Euro per turbine each year to adjacent municipalities.

Finally, it was stressed in the panel discussion on stakeholder and community engagement at the WindEurope event that engagement efforts should extend beyond the

¹Here, cultural change refers to a shift in the organizational culture within the wind energy industry, encompassing fundamental beliefs and values about community engagement that shape the industry's practices.

permitting and building phase and not only apply to energy plants but also to supporting infrastructure, such as transmission lines. For example, during the panel discussion, the Irish grid operator EirGrid shared their positive experiences with a pro-active community engagement approach.

In summary, while awareness of the relevance of good community engagement is increasing, there is still a long way to go with an urgent need to change mindsets, motivations, practices – and maybe even regulations. As summarized by one of the interviewed developers: “I think there are companies that are at the forefront of it because it is in their heart. Other companies are trying to follow, and then there are also the rotten apples that will never do it” (Developer 4).

A note on the method and limitations

This is not a systematic assessment but rather an exploration of current developer practices based on conveniently sampled interviews with four developers at the WindEurope Annual Event 2023. It was decided to anonymize the developers' names because this paper's goal is not to highlight the practices of specific developers but to discern some overall patterns of engagement approaches in the industry. Unfortunately, the author did not have the opportunity to interview residents about their experiences with the respective developers. Therefore, the findings are based on the developers' perspectives. The author conducted and audio-recorded the semi-structured interviews with the developers and later automatically transcribed them using Amberscript. The author did the unstructured interview with the social scientist in collaboration with a second interviewer. The interview was videotaped and automatically transcribed using Microsoft Teams. All interview transcripts were analyzed through open coding.

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